

Table 1. Reaction of resistance to W1, P1, and/or T1 isolates in progeny of resistant/susceptible combinations.

Combination	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ ² _c	P
		Total	Resistant plants (no.)	Susceptible plants (no.)			
Chengte 232/Nonghu 6	RRR ^a	212	195	17	15:1	0.8503	0.50-0.25
Nongken 58/Nonghu 6	RRR ^a	196	148	48	3:1	0.0068	>0.90
Tetep/Nonghu 6	R ^b	180	168	12	15:1	0.0059	>0.90

^aThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to P1, and the third to T1. ^bReaction to T1.

Table 2. Segregation for resistance to W1, P1, or T1 isolates in progeny of resistant/resistant combinations.

Combination	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ ² _c	P
		Total	Resistant plants (no.)	Susceptible plants (no.)			
Chengte 232/Nonghu 58	RR ^a	204	204	0			
Chengte 232/Tetep	R ^b	306	300	6	255:1	15.5633	<0.005
Chengte 232/CBB 3	RR ^c	188	188	0			
Nongken 58/CBB 3	RR ^c	204	204	0			
Chengte 232/CBB 4	RR ^a	195	190	5	63:1	0.7040	0.50-0.25
Nongken 58/CBB 4	RR ^a	210	195	15	15:1	0.1537	0.75-0.50

^aThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to P1. ^bReaction to T1. ^cThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to T1.

All materials were planted in the field and inoculated at the booting stage (after dipping scissors into a bacterial suspension containing 10⁹ cells/ml). Different tillers were inoculated with the different isolates and marked with different colors. Disease reaction was assessed after 3 wk using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Plants with scores of 1-3 were classified as resistant and those with scores of 4-9 as susceptible.

Chengte 232 and Tetep each carried two resistance genes for these isolates, while Nongken 58 carried one (Table 1). Allelism tests indicated one of the two genes in Chengte 232 was allelic to Xa-3, which was derived from Nongken 58. Apparently, the resistance genes of Tetep were not transferred into Chengte 232 (Table 2). The other gene of Chengte 232, however, was probably derived from Kongkewan ■

Analysis of resistance gene for blast in Chengte 232

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We analyzed the resistance genes and their allelism of Chengte 232 and its resistance donors using blast fungus isolates ZB1 (926) and P-2b (Japan). Chengte 232 and its resistance donors, Toride 1 and Tetep, are resistant to ZB1 and P-2b. Nonghu 6, which is susceptible to the isolates, was used as the susceptible parent.

Chengte 232, Toride 1, and Tetep were each crossed with Nonghu 6 to analyze the inheritance of resistance. We also made crosses among Chengte 232, Toride 1, and Tetep to test allelism of resistance genes.

All materials were planted in the field and inoculated at maximum tillering by injecting plants with a spore suspension of 1-2 x 10⁵ conidia/ml. Disease reaction was assessed at 7 d after inoculation using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Plants with scores of 1-3 were classified as resistant and those with

Table 1. Resistance reaction to ZB1 and P-2b races in progeny of resistant/susceptible combinations.

Combination	Race	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ ² _c	P
			Total	Resistant	Susceptible			
Chengte 232/Nonghu 6	ZB1	R ^a	189	143	46	3:1	0.0159	>0.90
	P-2b	R	189	143	46	3:1	0.0159	>0.90
Toride 1/Nonghu 6	ZB1	R	204	144	60	3:1	1.8889	0.25-0.10
	P-2b	R	204	144	60	3:1	1.8889	0.25-0.10
Tetep/Nonghu 6	ZB1	R	182	133	49	3:1	0.2637	0.75-0.50
	P-2b	R	182	166	16	15:1	1.5956	0.25-0.10

^aR = resistant.

Table 2. Segregation for resistance to ZB1 and P-2b races in progeny of resistant/resistant combinations.

Combination	Race	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ ² _c	P
			Total	Resistant	Susceptible			
Chengte 232/Toride 1	ZB1	R ^a	216	216	0			
	P-2b	R	216	216	0			
Chengte 232/Tetep	ZB1	R	169	162	7	15:1	0.9471	0.50-0.25
	P-2b	R	169	165	4	63:1	0.2841	0.75-0.50
Toride 1/Tetep	ZB1	R	178	168	10	15:1	0.0375	0.90-0.75
	P-2b	R	178	170	8	63:1	8.1330	<0.005

^aR = resistant.

scores of 4-9 as susceptible.

A single dominant gene controls resistance to ZB1 and P-2b in Chengte 232 and Toride 1. Tetep has one dominant gene for resistance to ZB1 and

two dominant duplicate genes for P-2b (Table 1). Allelism tests indicated that the genes of Chengte 232 are nonallelic to those of Tetep and those of Toride 1 are allelic (Table 2).

Resistance in Chengte 232 to the two isolates tested is conditioned by a single gene that is allelic or closely linked to a gene in its progenitor, Toride 1. We conclude, therefore, that Chengte 232 inherited the gene from Toride 1.

Because Toride 1 carries *Pi-z'*, it is likely that *Pi-z'* controls the resistance in Chengte 232. The resistance genes of Tetep, however, were not transferred into Chengte 232. ■

Pest resistance—insects

Screening of rice hybrids for resistance to whitebacked planthopper, *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath)

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Twenty-four rice experimental hybrids were screened for whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) resistance at the adult plant stage under natural conditions at Bhupindra Rice Research Substation, Rauni (a hot spot of the insect at seedling stage), and under artificial conditions in a glasshouse at PAU. The field experiments were replicated three times using a

randomized complete block design. The glasshouse experiment was replicated twice using a completely randomized design.

Number of insects/10 hills in the field was counted by tapping plants. Damage was scored in the glasshouse experiment using the 0-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (see table).

PERH188, PERH207, PERH210, and PERH225 were found to be moderately resistant under both conditions and PERH239, PERH288, and PERH690 were considered to be susceptible.

Similar results were recorded for nearly half of the entries under both conditions. Differences, however, were noted in PERH125, PERH229,

Screening of rice hybrids under natural conditions at a hot spot in Rauni and under artificial infestation conditions, 1993 kharif.

Hybrid	Parentage	Insects/10 hills at Rauni (no.)	Damage score (0-9 scale)
PERH1	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1106-6-2	66	6.9
PERH2	Pb.CMS 8 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	55	7.2
PERH3	Pb.CMS 10 A/PAU1106-6-2	60	5.2
PERH7	Pb.CMS 1 A/PAU1106-6-2	44	6.6
PERH9	Pb.CMS 1 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	61	6.8
PERH38	Pb.CMS 2 A/PR106	25	5.7
PERH46	Pb.CMS 4 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	61	6.3
PERH125	Pb.CMS 8 A/IR13292-5-3	39	7.9
PERH134	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-1-1	145	5.8
PERH135	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	77	6.9
PERH188	Pb.CMS 10 A/PAU1106-5-4	39	4.5
PERH207	Pb.CMS 10 A/PR106	53	4.6
PERH210	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR32841-46-1-1	34	3.2
PERH225	Pb.CMS 2 A/IR32841-46-1-1	35	5.0
PERH229	Pb.CMS 2 A/PAU1106-21-4	191	4.1
PERH239	Pb.CMS 3 A/IR31432-6-2-1R	138	7.5
PERH244	Pb.CMS 3 A/PAU1106-21-4	165	3.6
PERH257	Pb.CMS 3 A/PR103	101	5.8
PERH288	Pb.CMS 8 A/PAU1126-29-1	193	8.1
PERH353	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR13292-5-3	34	6.7
PERH389	Pb.CMS 3 A/PAU1126-15-3-1	79	6.5
PERH588	Pb.CMS 1 A/IR31802-56-4	27	6.3
PERH577 A	Pb.CMS 2 A/IR31802-56-4	22	6.6
PERH690	Pb.CMS 58025 A/PAU1106-6-2	165	6.8
PR103 (check)	IR8/IR127-2-2	76	6.3
PR106 (check)	IR8//Peta*5/Belle Patna	83	8.4
PR108 (check)	Vijay/Ptb21	29	7.2
PR110 (check)	TN1/Patong 32//PR106	72	6.3

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PERH244, PERH353, PERH588, and PERH577 A. The differential behavior of the test entries suggests that rice germplasm should be screened for reaction to WBPH under both natural and artificial conditions. ■

Screening rice accessions for resistance to thrips

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Thrips, *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall), is a serious pest in rice nurseries in the tropical plains of Tamil Nadu. Both nymphs and adults can cause extensive damage to seedlings by feeding on the leaves, resulting in inward curling along the margins that can lead to scorching, wilting, and death.

In the first phase, we screened 122 accessions for reaction to thrips in the field during August 1992 and September 1993 at the Annamalai University Experimental Farm, Annamalaiagar. Each test entry was planted in moist soil in 0.7-m long rows, at a row space of 20 cm. Each entry was replicated three times, with one row per replication. Ptb33, the resistant check, and TN1, the